

ISSUES OF INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF SEWING AND KNITTING ENTERPRISES BY FINDING PROMISING MARKETS.

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the search for promising international markets of the sewing and knitting enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan was carried out using the cluster method and suggestions for increasing the export potential are presented.

Today, there is a sharp competition among participants in the market of world light industrial products. In the conditions of this competition, effective research in the field of marketing in order to increase the export potential is the demand of the times. In order to further improve and expand its material and technical base, a large amount of investments are being attracted. types of products are produced. Today, the main part of sewing and knitting enterprises is exported abroad. International marketing principles are effective in further development of activities in this regard. It is necessary to use i.

The term international marketing refers to production and sales activities within foreign countries.

UN experts include firms that sell their products and services to two or more countries as international companies.

At the same time, there are also the following other views: an international company differs from a local manufacturer in that its semi-finished products or

finished goods are not only sold within the country, but from one country to another.

International marketing recognized in the concept of a different approach to international entrepreneurship, which is formed in the local market and operates in the international market, does not fully reveal its content to the definitions of "differentiation between countries" and the awakening methods of marketing in the foreign and domestic market as fundamental views of how people feel.

Also interesting is the following definition given by V. I. Cherenkov, according to him, international marketing is a philosophy of international business and simultaneously commercial and non-commercial intellectual technology of this business.

International marketing can be understood as:

- selling goods or services outside their country;
- if marketing activities are carried out by the company in the following cases:

a) a branch of the firm acting as a producer or seller in the foreign market or operating on the basis of cooperation with other enterprises;

b) controlling or exerting some influence on the marketing activities of a company belonging to another country.

R.A. Isaev studied the issue of improving the organizational and management mechanisms of the implementation of the integrated complex system strategy in the enterprises of the textile industry and analyzed the problems of increasing the export potential.

The research was based on the research results of foreign and local researchers on the topic, and methods such as statistical sampling, observation, comparison, and expert evaluation were used.

Analysis and assessment of the state of international markets is closely related to the determination of attractiveness and competitive advantage in this market.

The attractiveness of the market is considered as a set of factors that describe the strategic success of a firm entering a certain market. The attractiveness of the market has the form of quantitative-qualitative descriptions expressed by the

dynamics of its volume and quality, such as the supply of energy and raw materials.

In order to evaluate the attractiveness of the market, in most cases, the method of export price is used, and each criterion is evaluated on scales with points.

- market size capacity - the volume of products sold in this country in a certain period of time in natural or value measures;

- the growth rate of the country's market is determined using an index that represents the growth of this market size in a certain period of time;

- composition of consumers - a group of large, medium and small consumers who buy this type of product in the country's market;

- grade range;

- consumer purchasing power;

- market entry barriers;

- level of political and economic risks;

- other external factors.

The level of market attractiveness and competitive advantage in the international arena is realized in its segmentation.

The general scheme of selecting a promising market in international marketing has the appearance of a four-stage model (drawing)

Initial market selection (possible market selection and selection procedures and selection criteria)
Macro segmentation
Defining the market segment
Export market

Figure 1. Four-stage model of market selection.

This model is designed for the selection of the export market. Some of its stages may be somewhat different in the conditions of different companies. By default, the stages of initial market assessment and final prospective market selection are preserved

in all cases. Due to the large number of international markets in the world economy, the company has to choose among all countries. how many stages it is required to perform. One of the methods of making such a selection is the initial selection method.

The technique and technology of this process should be very simple, it should be a superficial and fast-solving database.

The results of the analysis of the export geography of sewing and knitting enterprises operating in our republic show that the main market segment of these enterprises is the CIS countries. Therefore, in the process of research, we set the goal of developing measures for the formation of an effective marketing system in this segment of the international market of sewing and knitting products of our republic.

In our research, we found it necessary to study the consumer market of sewing and knitting enterprises engaged in export in our republic for the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) in two directions:

- market research methods;
- marketing globalization problem and psychographic market research.

In international business practice, market research is carried out by evaluating using a standard technique based on several criteria. This method is effective if the number of markets being studied is not too high. If the number of markets is large, the effectiveness of such an analysis method is limited, because the internal group variation is not taken into account. In addition, additive Various factors that are not considered in the evaluation (for example, taken into account in the formation of marketing strategy) are not without benefit if they are taken into account in market research.

It is proposed to use methods that allow the use of relative sizes and the cluster-analysis method in the collective market study. This approach has the following characteristics: it is distinguished by its

simplicity and reliability; it allows to classify objects according to a predetermined level of occurrence; it allows to use simple methods of discriminant analysis.

In our study, a method of studying the market of the CIS countries using this method is proposed.

Using cluster analysis, the market of the CIS countries was analyzed using the following criteria: market capacity, demand description, access to sales channels, intensity of competition, competition from local goods, territorial closure of the market, price range, market attractiveness. The assessment is made based on the grouping of statistical data on the existing legal norms in the countries of the CIS countries where the foreign trade turnover has been studied and on the evaluation of exports.

In order to facilitate the analysis, the main consumer countries were ranked as follows: 1-Azerbaijan; 2-Armenia; 3-Belarus; 4-Georgia; 5-Kazakhstan; 6-Kyrgyzstan; 7-Moldova; 8-Russia; 9-Tajikistan; 10-Turkmenistan; 11-Ukraine.

In the first stage of the analysis, the coefficient of market penetration was determined according to the amount of the ratio in the classification of groups. If it is higher than 0.5, then the coefficient of market penetration is equal to the amount of the calculated ratio. the market access coefficient is set at the level of K_j . This coefficient shows the proximity of classified markets to each other according to all criteria up to the level of this coefficient. In the second stage of the analysis, the proximity of two markets according to one criterion was evaluated using private proximity coefficients (K_j). According to the calculation method, two

market integral proximity coefficients (K_j) were calculated according to all criteria. It should be noted that if any private coefficients are smaller than the market entry coefficient, integral coefficients are not considered, and these markets are not combined into one group. In the fourth stage of the analysis, the primary grouping of the markets was carried out and the calculated integral indicators were placed in the matrix. As a result of processing the research results, Azerbaijan (1) and Turkmenistan (10), Belarus (3) and Tajikistan (9), Kazakhstan (5) and Russia (8), Kyrgyzstan (6) markets were combined into one group. At the fifth stage of the analysis, the grouping of secondary markets is carried out, and based on the results, a second matrix was built. Here, too, groups with a lower index than the market penetration coefficient are not combined with each other. After secondary grouping, 12 and 15 (Azerbaijan, Georgia and Turkmenistan markets), groups 16 and 17 (Kazakhstan, Russia, Kyrgyzstan markets) were merged.

It should be noted that in the results of the research, the secondary grouping was considered as the final result, and the 5th group appeared. These groups include markets close to each other. This result is used in the marketing strategy developed

to increase the efficiency of the export potential of light industrial products in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

After the market segmentation and brand positioning strategies are developed, the branding strategy is developed.

Brand formation in sewing and knitting enterprises is a unique complex process, which is carried out on the basis of brand strategy development. N.M. Muminova proposed in her research to divide the brand strategy into two types - monobranding and multibranding strategies, depending on the content.

The monobranding strategy involves the sale of goods of the same brand through trade channels. It is appropriate to use this strategy in comparison with monopoly goods in markets with strong demand for the product type. And the use of the multibranding strategy in order to expand the market segment for the development of distribution channels of goods in markets with strong competition will bring positive results. Our research shows that the support of using multi-branding strategy in expanding the sales market of certain products is expanding in the food and household service industries. We suggest the integrated use of two brand strategies for sewing and knitting products.

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